

Supplementary Information 6: Sample preparation

Specimens of *Campanile symbolicum* (**C2**) and *C. giganteum* (**E1**, **E2** and **E3**) were cleaned of any surrounding coarse grained sediment using a soft brush and cold water. Prepared shells were further cleaned in water at room temperature in an ultrasonic bath and predrilled to remove any features on the outside of the shell that could be visually distinguished as being altered or not part of the shells. In this cleaning process, any organisms attached to the outer side of the shell were gently removed using a slow rotating handheld drill (Dremel 3000, Robert Bosch Tool Corp., Mount Prospect, IL, USA) equipped with a tungsten carbide drill tip. Shells **C2**, **E2** and **E3** were sampled at intervals of 5-10 mm in the direction of growth along the helix using the same handheld drill. Sampling for stable isotope analysis was carried out by abrading material in a groove perpendicular to the growth direction using a dental drill equipped with a 1 mm wide diamond coated drill bit. Care was taken to sample only the visually well-preserved shell aragonite and to preferentially sample aragonite close to the suture rather than in the center of the whorl to prevent contamination of samples with secondary aragonite precipitated inside the whorl, which is closer to the outside surface of the shell in the center of the whorl (see **S4**).

Since **E1** was too much affected by boring to allow external sampling of well-preserved aragonite, the well-preserved aragonite of this shell was sampled on a polished cross section. To allow comparison between stable isotope compositions of aragonite on the outer shell wall and the inside of the shell, a second transect was sampled along the columella of the modern shell (**C2**; see **S12**).

After external sampling, all shells were fully embedded in Araldite® epoxy resin and cut longitudinally using a 1 mm wide slow-rotating precision saw with a water cooled diamond coated blade. Longitudinal cross sections were polished using increasingly high grade polishing paper on a water-cooled rotating polishing disk up to grit size P3600 (3 µm particle size). The interior of all specimens revealed exceptionally well-preserved aragonite with clearly visible growth laminations.

Fragments from the unpolished side of the shells were prepared for microscopic analyses. Several parts of the cross sections through the columella of **E1** were prepared into thick sections for cathodoluminescence microscopy and thin sections for visible light microscopy (see **S1**). Broken fragments from the outside of the shell (including borings), the internal shell walls, the columella, the aperture and the secondary aragonite precipitated inside the whorl were prepared on resin stubs and sputter coated with carbon for Scanning Electron Microscope analyses (see **S1**).